

Electromagnetic Wave Function and Equation, Lorentz Force in Rindler Spacetime

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Abstract: In the general relativity theory, we find the electro-magnetic wave function and equation in Rindler space-time. Specially, this article is that electromagnetic wave equation is corrected by the gauge fixing equation in Rindler space-time. We define the force in Rindler space-time. We find Lorentz force (electromagnetic force) by electro-magnetic field transformations in Rindler space-time. In the inertial frame, Lorentz force is defined as 4-dimensional force. Hence, we had to obtain 4-dimensional force in Rindler space-time. We define energy-momentum in Rindler space-time.

Keywords: General relativity theory, Rindler spacetime; Electro-magnetic wave equation; Electromagnetic wave function; Lorentz force; Electro-magnetic field transformation, Energy-momentum

PACS Number: 04, 04.90. +e, 03.30, 41.20

1. INTRODUCTION

In the general relativity theory, our article's aim is that we find the electro-magnetic wave equation and function and Lorentz force by electro-magnetic field transformations in Rindler space-time. This article correct the article "Electromagnetic Field Equation and Lorentz Gauge in Rindler space-time" about the existence proof of electromagnetic wave function and equation. We define energy-momentum in Rindler space-time.

The Rindler coordinate is

$$\begin{aligned}
 ct &= \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \\
 x &= \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) - \frac{c^2}{a_0}, y = \xi^2, z = \xi^3
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
 cdt &= c \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) d\xi^0 \left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right) + \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) d\xi^1 \\
 dx &= c \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) d\xi^0 \left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right) + \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) d\xi^1, dy = d\xi^2, dz = d\xi^3
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} &= \frac{c \partial \xi^0}{c \partial t} \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^0} + \frac{\partial \xi^1}{c \partial t} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^1} \\
 &= \frac{\cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right)}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} \frac{\partial}{c \partial \xi^0} - \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^1}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} &= \frac{c \partial \xi^0}{\partial x} \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^0} + \frac{\partial \xi^1}{\partial x} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^1} \\ &= -\frac{\sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right)}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} \frac{\partial}{c \partial \xi^0} + \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^1} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial y} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^2}, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^3} \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 &= \frac{1}{c^2 \left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right)^2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^0}\right)^2 - \nabla_{\xi}^2 \\ \vec{\nabla} &= \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial}{\partial z}\right), \quad \vec{\nabla}_{\xi} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^1}, \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^2}, \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^3}\right) \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

2. CORRECTED ELECTROMAGNETIC WAVE EQUATION IN THE RINDLER SPACE-TIME

The electro-magnetic field $(\vec{E}, \vec{B})$ is in the inertial frame,

$$\vec{E} = -\vec{\nabla} \phi - \frac{\partial \vec{A}}{c \partial t}, \quad \vec{B} = \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{A} \tag{5}$$

Hence, we can define the electro-magnetic field $(\vec{E}_{\xi}, \vec{B}_{\xi})$ in Rindler space-time [1].

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{E}_{\xi} &= -\frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} \vec{\nabla}_{\xi} \left\{ \phi_{\xi} \left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)^2 \right\} - \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} \frac{\partial \vec{A}_{\xi}}{c \partial \xi^0} \\ \vec{B}_{\xi} &= \vec{\nabla}_{\xi} \times \vec{A}_{\xi} \\ \text{In this time, } \vec{\nabla}_{\xi} &= \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^1}, \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^2}, \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^3}\right), \quad \vec{A}_{\xi} = (A_{\xi^1}, A_{\xi^2}, A_{\xi^3}) \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Hence, Lorentz gauge condition is in Rindler space-time [1],

$$\phi_{\xi} \rightarrow \phi_{\xi} - \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial \xi^0} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)}, \quad \vec{A}_{\xi} \rightarrow \vec{A}_{\xi} + \vec{\nabla}_{\xi} \Lambda, \quad \Lambda \text{ is a scalar function.} \tag{7}$$

$$A^{\mu}{}_{;\mu} = \frac{\partial A^{\mu}}{\partial \xi^{\mu}} + \Gamma^{\mu}{}_{\mu\rho} A^{\rho} \rightarrow \partial_{\mu} (A^{\mu} + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_{\nu} \Lambda) + \Gamma^0{}_{01} (A^1 + \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial \xi^1}) \tag{8}$$

Lorentz gauge fix condition is in Rindler space-time [1],

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \phi_{\xi}}{\partial \xi^0} + \vec{\nabla}_{\xi} \cdot \vec{A}_{\xi} + \frac{A_{\xi^1}}{c^2} \frac{a_0}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} \\ &\rightarrow \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \phi_{\xi}}{\partial \xi^0} + \vec{\nabla}_{\xi} \cdot \vec{A}_{\xi} + \frac{A_{\xi^1}}{c^2} \frac{a_0}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} - \left[\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)^2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^0}\right)^2 - \nabla_{\xi}^2 \right] \Lambda + \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{a_0}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} \\ &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Hence, the gauge equation is

$$\left[\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)^2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^0}\right)^2 - \nabla_{\xi^2}^2 \right] \Lambda - \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{a_0}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} = 0 \quad (10)$$

We can use Eq(10) as an electromagnetic wave equation because we can apply electromagnetic wave function instead of the gauge function Λ to Eq(10) in Rindler space-time. Hence,

$$\left[\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)^2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^0}\right)^2 - \nabla_{\xi^2}^2 \right] E_{\xi^1} - \frac{\partial E_{\xi^1}}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{a_0}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} = 0$$

$$\left[\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)^2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^0}\right)^2 - \nabla_{\xi^2}^2 \right] B_{\xi^1} - \frac{\partial B_{\xi^1}}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{a_0}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\left[\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)^2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^0}\right)^2 - \nabla_{\xi^2}^2 \right] E_y - \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{a_0}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} = 0$$

$$\left[\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)^2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^0}\right)^2 - \nabla_{\xi^2}^2 \right] B_y - \frac{\partial B_y}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{a_0}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\left[\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)^2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^0}\right)^2 - \nabla_{\xi^2}^2 \right] E_z - \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{a_0}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} = 0$$

$$\left[\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)^2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^0}\right)^2 - \nabla_{\xi^2}^2 \right] B_z - \frac{\partial B_z}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{a_0}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} = 0 \quad (13)$$

The electro-magnetic wave function is

$$E_x = E_{x0} \sin\Phi, E_y = E_{y0} \sin\Phi, E_z = E_{z0} \sin\Phi$$

$$B_x = B_{x0} \sin\Phi, B_y = B_{y0} \sin\Phi, B_z = B_{z0} \sin\Phi \quad (14)$$

$$E_{\xi^1} = E_x = E_{x0} \sin\Phi, B_{\xi^1} = B_x = B_{x0} \sin\Phi$$

$$E_{\xi^2} = E_y \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) - B_z \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right),$$

$$= (E_{y0} \sin\Phi) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) - (B_{z0} \sin\Phi) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right)$$

$$B_{\xi^2} = B_y \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) + E_z \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right)$$

$$= (B_{y0} \sin\Phi) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) + (E_{z0} \sin\Phi) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right)$$

$$E_{\xi^3} = E_z \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) + B_y \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) = (E_{z0} \sin\Phi) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) + (B_{y0} \sin\Phi) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right)$$

$$B_{\xi^3} = B_z \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) - E_y \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right)$$

$$= (B_{z0} \sin\Phi) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) - (E_{y0} \sin\Phi) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \quad (15)$$

$$\Phi = \omega\left(t - l \frac{x}{c} - m \frac{y}{c} - n \frac{z}{c}\right),$$

$$= \omega\left\{\left(\frac{c}{a_0} + \frac{\xi^1}{c}\right) \left(\sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) - l \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right)\right) + \frac{c}{a_0} - m \frac{\xi^2}{c} - n \frac{\xi^3}{c}\right\},$$

$$l^2 + m^2 + n^2 = 1 \quad (16)$$

3. ELECTRO-MAGNETIC FORCE IN RINDLER SPACE-TIME

In inertial frame, Lorentz 4-force is

$$F^0 = m_0 \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{cdt}{d\tau}\right) = q \frac{\vec{u}}{c} \cdot \vec{E} \quad (17)$$

$$\vec{F} = m_0 \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{d\vec{x}}{d\tau}\right) = q\left[\vec{E} + \frac{\vec{u}}{c} \times \vec{B}\right], \quad \vec{u} = \frac{d\vec{x}}{dt} \quad (18)$$

We want to obtain the Lorentz 4-force in Rindler space-time. Hence, we define the force in Rindler space-time.

$$F_{\xi}^0 = m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{cd\xi^0}{d\tau}\right)$$

$$\vec{F}_{\xi} = m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{d\vec{\xi}}{d\tau}\right) \quad (19)$$

Or

$$F_{\xi}^{\mu} = m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{d\xi^{\mu}}{d\tau}\right) \quad (20)$$

Hence, 4-force is in inertial frame

$$F^{\alpha} = m_0 \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dx^{\alpha}}{d\tau}\right) \quad (21)$$

In this time, Minkowski force is in inertial frame or in Rindler space-time [13].

$$f^{\alpha} = m_0 \frac{d}{d\tau} \left(\frac{dx^{\alpha}}{d\tau}\right) = m_0 \frac{d^2 x^{\alpha}}{d\tau^2} \quad (22)$$

$$f_{\xi}^{\mu} = m_0 \frac{d}{d\tau} \left(\frac{d\xi^{\mu}}{d\tau}\right) = m_0 \frac{d^2 \xi^{\mu}}{d\tau^2} \quad (23)$$

Minkowski force is

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^\alpha &= m_0 \frac{d^2 x^\alpha}{d\tau^2} = m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial x^\alpha}{\partial \xi^\mu} \frac{d\xi^\mu}{d\tau} \right) \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} \\
 &= m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial x^\alpha}{\partial \xi^\mu} \right) \frac{d\xi^\mu}{d\tau} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} + m_0 \frac{\partial x^\alpha}{\partial \xi^\mu} \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{d\xi^\mu}{d\tau} \right) \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} \\
 &= m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial x^\alpha}{\partial \xi^\mu} \right) \frac{d\xi^\mu}{d\tau} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} + F_\xi^\mu \frac{\partial x^\alpha}{\partial \xi^\mu} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} \\
 F_\xi^\mu &= m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{d\xi^\mu}{d\tau} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^0 &= m_0 \frac{cd^2 t}{d\tau^2} = m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi^0} \right) \frac{cd\xi^0}{d\tau} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} + F_\xi^0 \frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi^0} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} \\
 &+ m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{c\partial t}{\partial \xi^1} \right) \frac{d\xi^1}{d\tau} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} + F_\xi^1 \frac{c\partial t}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau}
 \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^1 &= m_0 \frac{d^2 x}{d\tau^2} = m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^0} \right) \frac{cd\xi^0}{d\tau} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} + F_\xi^0 \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^0} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} \\
 &+ m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^1} \right) \frac{d\xi^1}{d\tau} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} + F_\xi^1 \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau}
 \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

$$F_\xi^0 = m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{cd\xi^0}{d\tau} \right), F_\xi^1 = m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{d\xi^1}{d\tau} \right)$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &F_\xi^0 \frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi^0} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} + F_\xi^1 \frac{c\partial t}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} \\
 &= f^0 - m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi^0} \right) \frac{cd\xi^0}{d\tau} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} - m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{c\partial t}{\partial \xi^1} \right) \frac{d\xi^1}{d\tau} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} = A
 \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &F_\xi^0 \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^0} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} + F_\xi^1 \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} \\
 &= f^1 - m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^0} \right) \frac{cd\xi^0}{d\tau} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} - m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^1} \right) \frac{d\xi^1}{d\tau} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} = B
 \end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

If we represent by the matrix,

$$\begin{pmatrix} A \\ B \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi^0} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} & \frac{c\partial t}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} \\ \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^0} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} & \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} F_\xi^0 \\ F_\xi^1 \end{pmatrix} \tag{29}$$

In this time, Rindler coordinate is

$$ct = \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1 \right) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c} \right), x = \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1 \right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c} \right) - \frac{c^2}{a_0}, y = \xi^2, z = \xi^3 \tag{30}$$

So,

$$\frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi^0} = \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c^2}, \quad \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^0} = \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c^2}$$

$$\frac{c \partial t}{\partial \xi^1} = \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right), \quad \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^1} = \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \tag{31}$$

Hence,

$$Det = \left(\frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi^0} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^1} - \frac{c \partial t}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^0}\right) \left(\frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau}\right)^2 = \left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right) \left(\frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau}\right)^2 \tag{32}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{pmatrix} F_{\xi^0} \\ F_{\xi^1} \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right) \left(\frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau}\right)^2} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau} & -\frac{c \partial t}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau} \\ -\frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^0} \frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau} & \frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi^0} \frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} A \\ B \end{pmatrix} \tag{33}$$

Hence,

$$F_{\xi^0} = \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right) \left(\frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau}\right)^2} \left[A \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau} - B \frac{c \partial t}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau} \right]$$

$$= \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right) \left(\frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau}\right)^2} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^1} \left[f^0 - m_0 \frac{d}{d \xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi^0}\right) c \left(\frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau}\right)^2 - m_0 \frac{d}{d \xi^0} \left(\frac{c \partial t}{\partial \xi^1}\right) \frac{d \xi^1}{d \tau} \frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau} \right]$$

$$- \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right) \left(\frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau}\right)^2} \frac{c \partial t}{\partial \xi^1} \left[f^1 - m_0 \frac{d}{d \xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^0}\right) c \left(\frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau}\right)^2 - m_0 \frac{d}{d \xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^1}\right) \frac{d \xi^1}{d \tau} \frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau} \right] \tag{34}$$

As,

$$F_{\xi^1} = \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right) \left(\frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau}\right)^2} \left[-A \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^0} \frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau} + B \frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi^0} \frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau} \right]$$

$$= -\frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right) \left(\frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau}\right)^2} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^0} \left[f^0 - m_0 \frac{d}{d \xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi^0}\right) c \left(\frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau}\right)^2 - m_0 \frac{d}{d \xi^0} \left(\frac{c \partial t}{\partial \xi^1}\right) \frac{d \xi^1}{d \tau} \frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau} \right]$$

$$+ \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right) \left(\frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau}\right)^2} \frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi^0} \left[f^1 - m_0 \frac{d}{d \xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^0}\right) c \left(\frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau}\right)^2 - m_0 \frac{d}{d \xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^1}\right) \frac{d \xi^1}{d \tau} \frac{d \xi^0}{d \tau} \right] \tag{35}$$

In this time,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi^0} \right) &= \frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0} \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c^2} + \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0^2}{c^3}, \\ \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^0} \right) &= \frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c^2} + \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0^2}{c^3} \\ \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{c \partial t}{\partial \xi^1} \right) &= \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c}, \quad \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^1} \right) = \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c} \end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

Therefore, Eq (34) is by Eq (31), Eq (36). Lorentz force F_{ξ}^0 is in Rindler space-time.

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\xi}^0 &= \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right) \left(\frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau}\right)} \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \\ &\times \left[f^0 - m_0 \left\{ \frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0} \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c^2} + \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0^2}{c^3} \right\} c \left(\frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau}\right)^2 \right. \\ &\left. - m_0 \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c} \frac{d\xi^1}{d\tau} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} \right] \\ &- \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right) \left(\frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau}\right)} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \\ &\times \left[f^1 - m_0 \left\{ \frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c^2} + \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0^2}{c^3} \right\} c \left(\frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau}\right)^2 \right. \\ &\left. - m_0 \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c} \frac{d\xi^1}{d\tau} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} \right] \end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

Therefore, Eq (35) is by Eq (31), Eq (36). Lorentz force F_{ξ}^1 is in Rindler space-time.

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\xi}^1 &= - \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right) \left(\frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau}\right)} \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c^2} \\ &\times \left[f^0 - m_0 \left\{ \frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0} \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c^2} + \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0^2}{c^3} \right\} c \left(\frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau}\right)^2 \right. \\ &\left. - m_0 \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c} \frac{d\xi^1}{d\tau} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right) \left(\frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau}\right)} \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c^2} \\
 & \times \left[f^1 - m_0 \left\{ \frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c^2} + \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0^2}{c^3} \right\} c \left(\frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau}\right)^2 \right. \\
 & \left. - m_0 \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c} \frac{d\xi^1}{d\tau} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} \right] \tag{38}
 \end{aligned}$$

In this time, the transformation of electromagnetic field is [1]

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_x &= E_{\xi^1}, \\
 E_y &= E_{\xi^2} \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) + B_{\xi^3} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right), \\
 E_z &= E_{\xi^3} \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) - B_{\xi^2} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \\
 B_x &= B_{\xi^1}, \\
 B_y &= B_{\xi^2} \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) - E_{\xi^3} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \\
 B_z &= B_{\xi^3} \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) + E_{\xi^2} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \tag{39}
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^0 &= F^0 \frac{dt}{d\tau} = q \frac{\vec{u}}{c} \cdot \vec{E} \frac{dt}{d\tau} = q \frac{\vec{u}'}{c} \cdot \vec{E}, \vec{u} = \frac{d\vec{x}}{dt}, \vec{u}' = \frac{d\vec{x}}{d\tau} \\
 &= q \frac{1}{c} \left[\frac{dx}{d\tau} E_x + \frac{dy}{d\tau} E_y + \frac{dz}{d\tau} E_z \right], \frac{dx}{d\tau} = \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^0} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} + \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{d\xi^1}{d\tau} \\
 &+ \frac{d\xi^2}{d\tau} \left\{ E_{\xi^2} \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) + B_{\xi^3} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \right\} + \frac{d\xi^3}{d\tau} \left\{ E_{\xi^3} \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) - B_{\xi^2} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \right\} \tag{40}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$f^1 = F^1 \frac{dt}{d\tau},$$

$$F^1 = q \left[E_x + \frac{1}{c} (u_y B_z - u_z B_y) \right], \vec{u} = \frac{d\vec{x}}{dt}$$

$$f^1 = F^1 \frac{dt}{d\tau} = q \left[E_x \frac{dt}{d\tau} + \frac{1}{c} \left(\frac{dy}{d\tau} B_z - \frac{dz}{d\tau} B_y \right) \right], \frac{dt}{d\tau} = \frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi^0} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} + \frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{d\xi^1}{d\tau}$$

$$= q \left[\left\{ \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c^2} \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} + \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{1}{c} \frac{d\xi^1}{d\tau} \right\} E_{\xi^1} \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \frac{1}{c} \left\{ \frac{d\xi^2}{d\tau} (B_{\xi^3} \cosh(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}) + E_{\xi^2} \sinh(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c})) \right. \\
 & \left. - \frac{d\xi^3}{d\tau} (B_{\xi^2} \cosh(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}) - E_{\xi^3} \sinh(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c})) \right\} \quad (41)
 \end{aligned}$$

In Eq(24), f^2 is

$$f^2 = m_0 \frac{d^2 y}{d\tau^2} = F_{\xi}^2 \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau}, \quad F_{\xi}^2 = m_0 \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dy}{d\tau} \right) \frac{dt}{d\xi^0} = F^2 \frac{dt}{d\xi^0} \quad (42)$$

Therefore, Lorentz force F_{ξ}^2 is in Rindler space-time.

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{\xi}^2 & = m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{d\xi^2}{d\tau} \right) = F^2 \frac{dt}{d\xi^0} \\
 & = q \left[E_y + \frac{1}{c} (u_z B_x - u_x B_z) \right] \frac{dt}{d\xi^0} \\
 & = q \left\{ E_{\xi^2} \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) + B_{\xi^3} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \right\} \\
 & \times \left\{ \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c^2} + \frac{1}{c} \frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \right\} + \frac{1}{c} \left\{ \frac{d\xi^3}{d\xi^0} B_{\xi^1} \right. \\
 & \left. - \left\{ \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c} + \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0} \right\} \right. \\
 & \left. \times \left\{ B_{\xi^3} \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) + E_{\xi^2} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \right\} \right\} \quad (43)
 \end{aligned}$$

In Eq (24), f^3 is

$$f^3 = m_0 \frac{d^2 z}{d\tau^2} = F_{\xi}^3 \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau}, \quad F_{\xi}^3 = m_0 \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dz}{d\tau} \right) \frac{dt}{d\xi^0} = F^3 \frac{dt}{d\xi^0} \quad (44)$$

Therefore, Lorentz force F_{ξ}^3 is in Rindler space-time.

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{\xi}^3 & = m_0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \left(\frac{d\xi^3}{d\tau} \right) = F^3 \frac{dt}{d\xi^0} \\
 & = q \left[E_z + \frac{1}{c} (u_x B_y - u_y B_x) \right] \frac{dt}{d\xi^0} \\
 & = q \left\{ E_{\xi^3} \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) - B_{\xi^2} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \right\} \\
 & \times \left\{ \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c^2} + \frac{1}{c} \frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \frac{1}{c} \left\{ \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1 \right) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{a_0}{c} + \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{d\xi^1}{d\xi^0} \right\} \\
 & \times \left\{ B_{\xi^2} \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) - E_{\xi^3} \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \right\} - \frac{d\xi^2}{d\xi^0} B_{\xi^1} \left. \right\} \quad (45)
 \end{aligned}$$

4. ENERGY-MOMENTUM IN RINDLER SPACETIME

In initial frame, energy-momentum is

$$\vec{p} = m_0 \frac{d\vec{x}}{d\tau}, \quad E = m_0 c^2 \frac{dt}{d\tau} \quad (46)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_x &= m_0 \frac{dx}{d\tau} = m_0 \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^\alpha} \frac{d\xi^\alpha}{d\tau} \\
 &= m_0 \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^0} \frac{cd\xi^0}{d\tau} + m_0 \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{d\xi^1}{d\tau} \\
 &= m_0 \left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1 \right) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{cd\xi^0}{d\tau} + m_0 \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{d\xi^1}{d\tau} \quad (47)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 E &= m_0 c^2 \frac{dt}{d\tau} = m_0 c \frac{cdt}{\partial \xi^\alpha} \frac{d\xi^\alpha}{d\tau} \\
 &= m_0 c \frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi^0} \frac{cd\xi^0}{d\tau} + m_0 c \frac{\partial t}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{d\xi^1}{d\tau} \\
 &= m_0 c \left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1 \right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{cd\xi^0}{d\tau} + m_0 c \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{d\xi^1}{d\tau} \quad (48)
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we can define energy-momentum in Rindler spacetime.

$$\vec{p}_\xi = m_0 \frac{d\vec{\xi}}{d\tau}, \quad E_\xi = m_0 c^2 \left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1 \right) \frac{d\xi^0}{d\tau} \quad (49)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_x &= m_0 \frac{dx}{d\tau} = \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) \frac{E_\xi}{c} + \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) p_{\xi^1} \\
 E &= m_0 c^2 \frac{dt}{d\tau} = \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) E_\xi + \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) p_{\xi^1} c \\
 p_y &= m_0 \frac{dy}{d\tau} = m_0 \frac{d\xi^2}{d\tau} = p_{\xi^2}, \quad p_z = m_0 \frac{dz}{d\tau} = m_0 \frac{d\xi^3}{d\tau} = p_{\xi^3} \quad (50)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, general case is

$$E_\xi^2 - p_\xi^2 c^2 = m_0^2 c^4 \left[\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2} \right)^2 \frac{(d\xi^0)^2}{d\tau^2} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{d\vec{\xi} \cdot d\vec{\xi}}{d\tau^2} \right] = m_0^2 c^4 \quad (51)$$

In special case, light is

$$E_\xi = p_\xi c \quad (52)$$

5. CONCLUSION

We find the electro-magnetic wave equation and function and the electro-magnetic force in uniformly accelerated frame. We define energy-momentum in Rindler space-time.

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Citation: Sangwha-Yi, " Electromagnetic Wave Function and Equation, Lorentz Force in Rindler Spacetime", *International Journal of Advanced Research in Physical Science (IJARPS)*, vol. 5, no. 9, pp. 46-56, 2018.

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